

**5th INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
ON FOOD CONTAMINANTS:
CHALLENGES ON EXPOSURE ASSESSMENT,
HEALTH IMPACT AND SUSTAINABILITY OF FOOD SYSTEMS**

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

4-6 September, Campinas, Brazil

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CONFERENCE THEME
CHALLENGES ON EXPOSURE ASSESSEMENT,
HEALTH IMPACT AND SUSTAINABILITY
OF FOOD SYSTEMS

ICFC2023 BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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Dear Participants,

On behalf of the National Institute of Health Doctor Ricardo Jorge (INSA), we are honored and delighted to welcome you to the 5th International Conference on Food Contaminants (ICFC2023) and to receive you in the beautiful city of Campinas/São Paulo (SP), Brazil.

The conference will be held, for the first time outside Portugal, at the Instituto Agronomico de Campinas (IAC) in Campinas/SP, Brazil, from 4 to 6 September, as a hybrid event (presential and online) to broaden the scope of this international conference and to contribute to a closer scientific cooperation between Portugal and Brazil. The ICFC2023 aims to promote contact with realities of different continents in the fields of exposure assessments of food contaminants, human health and sustainability of food systems.

Like many countries around the world, Brazil and surrounding neighbors from Latin America, reported relevant problems concerning food safety and security, difficulties related to the sustainability of food systems and their transformation and a scarcity of available data on human exposure to chemicals and associated health effects.

In addition, scientific knowledge on these topics needs to be shared between different regions and populations, and preferably, locally addressed, to provide effective support for policymaker's decisions that aim to protect human health and the environment. Therefore, ICFC2023 represents a unique opportunity to debate different ideas, methods, and approaches on food contaminants and human health, towards desirable and sustainable food futures.

We wish you an excellent Conference!

Fernando de Almeida

Chairman of the Executive Board of the
National Institute of Health Doctor Ricardo Jorge, I.P.
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The Organizing Committee would like to welcome all of you and express sincere appreciation for choosing the city of Campinas, Brazil, as the venue for the 5th International Food Contaminants Conference (ICFC2023).

The ICFC2023 is organized by a joint effort of researchers from the National Institute of Health Doctor Ricardo Jorge (INSA), from Lisboa and the Centre for Environmental and Marine Studies (CESAM) of the University of Aveiro, both from Portugal and the Faculty of Animal Science and Food Engineering (FZEA/USP), from Brazil. The ICFC 2023 also has the support of the Brazilian Society of Science and Food Technology (SBCTA) and the São Paulo Research Foundation (FAPESP). This three days conference is an international forum to gather researchers from different continents, to share and discuss their findings regarding the broad and interdisciplinary field of food contaminants under the theme “Challenges in exposure assessment, health impact and sustainability of food systems”.

Following the rationality on the impact of food contaminants on human health of ICFC conferences (ICFC2015 <http://hdl.handle.net/10400.18/3214>, ICFC2017 <http://hdl.handle.net/10400.18/4882>, ICFC-2019 <http://hdl.handle.net/10400.18/7166> and ICFC2021 <http://hdl.handle.net/10400.18/7795>), ICFC2023 will address the challenges related to the i) occurrence of food contaminants worldwide; ii) exposure assessment and health impact; iii) health, environment and sustainability of food systems and iv) networking and societal concerns of food contaminants.

Participants at this conference are cordially invited to contribute with a full manuscript to the Special Issue on “Chemical Contaminants in Foods: Exposure Assessment, Health Impact & Sustainability of Food Systems” on Food Research International.

Throughout this conference, we hope to create an atmosphere where everyone, academia, professionals and students, can exchange ideas and establish collaborations.

We look forward to welcoming and hosting you in Campinas and hope this conference becomes an unforgettable moment.

Carlos Oliveira and Paula Alvito
Chairs of ICFC2023

P34 – Ethyl carbamate content and health risk associated to Serbian orange wines

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Introduction: Orange wine is a type of white wine made by leaving the grape skins and seeds in contact with the juice, creating a deep orange-hued product. Wine may contain various toxic compounds, including ethyl carbamate (EC) and mycotoxin ochratoxin A (OTA), probable and possible human carcinogen, respectively. EC can be formed from different precursors (urea, citrulline, cyanides) which could be produced during the process of fermentation, while OTA is produced by different *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium* fungus.

Methodology: A total of 24 Serbian orange wines were subjected to GC-MS analysis of EC and HPLC-FLD analysis of OTA. EC and OTA content were evaluated in terms of associated health risk, taking into account wine consumption on population average, regular drinkers only and chronic heavy drinkers, according to the World Health Organization data, as well as Serbian food consumption survey.

Results: Presence of OTA was not detected in any of the samples, hence the position 'no exposure, no risk' was taken. On the other hand, EC was quantified in half of the samples, in concentrations up to 16.8 µg/L. Resulting margins of exposure (MOE) were in the safe zone, above 10,000, at both mean and high exposure levels. Lifetime cancer risk (LCR) approach based on EC oral slope factor showed that tolerable risk of 1 extra lifetime cancer case per 100,000 persons was

exceeded in chronic heavy drinking and consumers only consumption scenarios at mean exposure of men and high exposure of women, while high exposure of men indicated risk concerns across all exposure scenarios. However, LCR based on EC virtually safe dose was negligible at both mean and high exposure levels, for both men and women, in every exposure scenario.

Conclusion: According to the World Health Organization, three million deaths every year result from the harmful use of alcohol. However, the well known connection between moderate wine consumption and substantial health benefit should not be ignored – it is necessary to secure that the benefit outweighs the risk, in case of orange or any other wine.